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by condensing 4-[N, N Bis-(2-chloroethyl) amino] benzaldehyde cyanohydrin with different amines⁵. The nitriles were treated with conc. sulphuric acid in order to get corresponding amides⁵. All the nitriles and amides were tested for antibacterial activity.

Where R=aryl, X = CN or CONH₂

Preparation and Antibacterial Activity of α -arylamino-[N, N bis-(2 chloroethyl)-amino]-Phenyl Acetonitriles and their Corresponding Amides

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THE majority of nitrogen mustard characterised by Bis-(2 chloroethyl)-amino group have been synthesised as anticancer agents¹. The property of nitrogen mustard vary widely with structural modification. Popp and Kirsch² prepared anil derivatives of 4-[N, N Bis-{2-chloroethyl)-amino]-benzaldehyde and tested against Dunning leukemia in rats. The hydrazones and thiosemicarbazones of above aldehyde have been prepared for anticancer activity^{3,4}. In view of this valid observation, we have synthesised various α -Arylamino-[N, N bis-(2 chloroethyl)-amino]-phenyl acetonitriles and their corresponding amides of type (I)

Experimental

a) Preparation of 4-[N, N Bis-(2-chloroethyl)-amino] benzaldehyde :

N, N Bis-(2 hydroxyethyl)-aniline was prepared by condensing aniline with ethylene chlorohydrine⁵. The product was then treated with dimethylformamide and phosphorus oxychloride to get the above aldehyde⁷.

b) Preparation of α -Arylamino-[N, N bis (2-chloroethyl)-amino]-phenyl acetonitriles :

The above aldehyde (0.01 mole) dissolved in ethanol (95%, 50 ml.) was added potassium cyanide (0.01 mole) in water (10 ml.) followed by glacial acetic acid (0.01 mole) with constant stirring. Amine (0.01 mole) dissolved in ethanol (95%, 85 ml.) was added and the reaction mixture kept at 25-30° for 24 hrs. The contents were diluted with cold water and the product obtained was crystallised from aqueous ethanol. (Physical. constants are recorded in table-1).

TABLE I—PHYSICAL CONSTANTS OF NITRILES

Sr. No.	R	Molecular formula	m. p. °C	Yield %	Calc. % Nitrogen	found
1.	Phenyl	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ N ₂ Cl ₂	100-01	89.2	12.06	12.0
2.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₂ Cl ₂	85-86	86.0	11.60	11.2
3.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₂ Cl ₂	120-21	81.1	11.60	11.5
4.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₂ Cl ₂	94-95	89.2	11.60	11.0
5.	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ ON ₂ Cl ₂	104-05	73.2	11.11	11.3
6.	<i>m</i> -Anisyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ ON ₂ Cl ₂	78-79	71.0	11.11	11.0
7.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ ON ₂ Cl ₂	75-76	89.0	11.11	10.9
8.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₂ Cl ₃	103-04	88.2	10.99	10.8
9.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₂ Cl ₃	120-21	77.0	10.99	11.1
10.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₂ Cl ₃	80-81	91.0	10.99	11.2
11.	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₂ Cl ₂ Br	87-88	88.2	9.83	9.5
12.	<i>p</i> -Arsenophenyl	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₂ Cl ₂ AS	79-81	87.0	10.90	10.5

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL CONSTANTS OF AMIDES

Sr. No.	R	Molecular formula	m. p. °C.	Yield %	% Nitrogen	
					calc.	found
1.	Phenyl	C ₁₈ H ₂₁ ON ₂ Cl ₂	107-08	72.0	11.47	11.10
2.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	C ₁₉ H ₂₃ ON ₂ Cl ₂	118-19	64.3	11.05	10.95
3.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	C ₁₉ H ₂₃ ON ₂ Cl ₂	125-26	60.0	11.05	11.20
4.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	C ₁₉ H ₂₃ ON ₂ Cl ₂	128-30	66.7	11.05	11.0
5.	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	C ₁₉ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂	195-96 d	72.0	10.60	10.4
6.	<i>m</i> -Anisyl	C ₁₉ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂	162-63	62.0	10.60	10.2
7.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	C ₁₉ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂	115-16	71.0	10.60	10.3
8.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ ON ₂ Cl ₂	113-14	67.0	10.50	10.8
9.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ ON ₂ Cl ₂	124-25	69.9	10.50	10.2
10.	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ ON ₂ Cl ₂ Br	140-42	70.0	9.43	9.0
11.	<i>p</i> -Arsenophenyl	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂ AS	88-89	66.0	8.88	9.0

c) Preparation of α -Arylamino-[N, N Bis-(2 chloroethyl)-amino]-phenyl acetamides :

α -Arylamino-[N, N bis-(2 chloroethyl)-amino]-phenyl acetonitriles (0.025 mole) was dissolved in concentrated sulphuric acid (10 ml.) below 10° and kept for 48 hrs. at room temperature. Contents were then poured into ice water and filtered. The filtrate was made alkaline by aqueous sodium hydroxide solution. The product obtained was crystallised from ethanol. (Physical constants are recorded in table 2).

Antibacterial Screening

The above compounds were tested for antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*. by cup plate method⁸ using ethanol (70%) as solvent. In case of nitriles *p*-anisyl derivative was highly active against *S. aureus* as compared to the other products, while phenyl derivative was active against both *E. coli*. as well as *S. aureus*. In case of amides *p*-tolyl derivative was found to be active against both *S. aureus* as well as *E. coli*.

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